

EVALUATION FOR THE STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITE MAGNESIUM OXIDE (MGO) BOARDS

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ABSTRACT

There is a continuous challenge for using new generation of composites from renewable natural resources to replace the less eco-friendly structural and non-structural materials in the construction industry.

MgO board is an emerging panel used in the residential building industry in China, Middle East and United States. It is highly sustainable, consumes low energy, resistant to fire, strong and resistant to mould and mildew. The addition of reinforcement component represented by Fibre Reinforced Polymer (FRP) strips compositely acting with MgO boards improves the strength and load carrying capacity of the system. The combination for these emerging construction materials is anticipated to provide a cost effective and structurally efficient framing system.

The main aim of this study is to develop a better understanding of the structural performance of a composite framing system (e.g., roof/floor/wall framing system) made up from the novel sustainable lightweight MgO boards in composite with FRP component.

Preliminary experimental investigation was carried out to determine the basic mechanical properties of the MgO material which showed notable strength performance in addition to its fire resistance capability. This paper presents the bending behaviour and strength improvement of 20 mm thick composite MgO boards achieved when reinforced with FRP strips.

The presented work forms part of a long-term strategy to develop and produce Portable Bushfire Shelters that can assist emergency and firefighting crews to plan and action in their firefighting roles in a reliable and predictable manner.

1 INTRODUCTION

Worldwide, recurring bushfire events have revealed that forest firefighting is a difficult and often dangerous task. Whenever firefighters attempt to contain a wildfire, there is a risk that emergency and firefighting crews may become surrounded by fire. Entrapment in bushfires can have tragic consequences, as was the case in the Linton Fire (Victoria, Australia) in December 1998 when five firefighters lost their lives.

Several attempts have been made in recent years to offer fire and rescue teams a safe environment while being entrapped and exposed to direct attack from uncontrolled fire through the introduction of fire shelters as a last resort for survival. However, such shelters have been constrained with their limited functionality in resisting prolonged fire events. For example, in the United States a fire shelter tent was developed to become the ultimate piece of equipment to use when conditions and time make survival is impossible during a bushfire.

Currently, portable fire shelters are not used in Australia, although an attempt was made to introduce a number of protection systems after the latest fatal bushfire events [1-2]. During the Victorian Black Saturday bushfires in 2009, it was found that some victims died in non-accredited bushfire shelters, which were deemed by the Victorian Building Commission to be unsafe, and potentially a death trap for the individuals shielding inside them [3]. Advice on enhancing safety for firefighters is limited as insufficient research has been conducted on the problem. Previous proposals have not adequately considered the shelters' portability, and flexibility in placing and relocating them between strategic zones without the need for extensive on-site mounting or demounting facilities.

This paper is aimed at investigating the strength of lightweight composite section formed by adhesively bounding Fibre Reinforced Polymer (FRP) strips to MgO boards. The proposed composite model is the key element in the development of lightweight bushfire portable shelter given MgO boards' high thermal resistance ability.

Recently, MgO boards have been utilized in Australia for several applications in the construction industry including wall sheathing as non-structural component and floor board covering component. In addition to the many advantages attained from utilizing MgO boards including environmental friendly (renewable and recyclable resource), low energy consumption, low cost and good specific mechanical properties; MgO boards have an ability to withstand fire flames and excessive level of high temperatures. In 2012, CSIRO carried out burnover field tests on fixed structures of which walls comprised appropriate insulation and had MgO boards as external skin. The tests proved that the structure resisted prolonged time periods at external temperature of over 1,200°C, whilst the internal temperature was less than 35°C [4, 5].

Research attempts have been made for the application of MgO boards in composite with lightweight reinforcing materials (e.g., polystyrene and fibre glass polyurethane) in order to develop various types of composite wall systems including road side acoustic panels and prefabricated wall systems in residential modular construction [6]. Results from experimental work conducted by Manalo [6] on the shear bracing performance of composite walls made from glass fibre reinforced rigid polyurethane foam sheathed with MgO board, revealed that the behaviour of such composite system is governed by the strength of MgO boards, and it showed almost similar performance to that of other available composite wall systems. Furthermore, Manalo recommended the use of thicker MgO board that would increase the stiffness and the resistance in diagonal tension resulting in higher shear strength [6].

Although the structural behaviour of prefabricated composite wall systems has been investigated by several research teams [7-10], there is little acceptance for their use in the construction industry due to the lack of design standards and limited knowledge on their long-term performance [11]. Hence, a detailed understanding of the structural performance of new prefabricated wall system is necessary in order to enable emerging composite materials to provide efficient solutions similar to the one available for the conventional framing materials.

This paper aims to evaluate the strength performance of MgO boards reinforced with fibre polymer based material through simulated testing. A presentation for the conducted experimental program is presented in section 2. Test results and observed failure modes for the tested specimens are presented in section 3. An analytical model for estimating the bending capacity of the proposed composite model is presented and evaluated in section 4.

2 TESTED SPECIMENS AND EXPERIMENT SETUP

The experimental work presented in this section demonstrates the bending behaviour of the MgO-FRP composite section in comparison with unreinforced MgO board specimens. Three-point bending tests were conducted in accordance with Australian/New Zealand standard for cellulose-cement product – Part 2: Flat sheet [12]. 20 specimens were prepared for the test of which half were reinforced with FRP (Figure 1). The MgO specimens were cut from five MgO panels (as supplied) with the trimming being made along both the panel's width and length.

MgO boards were supplied by ModakBoards Australia and are classified as high density tongue and groove edge. The FRP strap was supplied by Sika and its mechanical properties are presented in Table 1, as provided by the supplier. The bonding between MgO boards and FRP strips was achieved using Sikadur 30 adhesive applied in accordance with the manufacturer's specifications. Figure 2 presents the test setup for 400 mm long specimen spanning 360 mm.

Figure 1: Tested specimens.

FRP type	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]	Young's Modulus E_{FRP} [MPa]	Strain at Break ϵ_{UFRP}	Mean Tensile Strength [MPa]
Sika CarboDur S512	50	1.2	165000	0.017	3100

Table 1: FBP composite component properties.

Figure 2: The 3-point bending test setup.

3 EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

This section presents results from the bending tests and observations made on the behaviour of the composite MgO boards under bending action including load-deflection diagrams and the observed flexure failure modes.

3.1 Unreinforced MgO boards bending strength behaviour

The midspan load-deflection behaviour of the 10 unreinforced MgO board specimens are shown in Figure 3. Consistent flexural stiffness was observed for all specimens showing typically linear load-

midspan deflection behaviour up to the maximum applied load. The averaged bending stiffness, maximum breaking force, bending stress and deflection (observed and estimated), are 0.43 kN/mm, 0.82 kN, 11 MPa and 2 mm, respectively. After attaining the maximum load capacity, flexural failure was initiated by tensile cracks at the bottom (tensioned) side of the specimens.

Figure 3: Load-deflection behaviour of unreinforced MgO board (left) and tensile cracks failure (right).

3.2 Composite MgO-FRP boards bending strength behaviour

Figure 4 presents test results for the 10 composite MgO board specimens in comparison with results from testing the plain MgO boards. The increase in stiffness of the reinforced section is found to be more than twofold (167%) of that for the plain section, with a maximum breaking force of 5.17 kN. The presence of the FRP component at the tensioned side of the specimens had obviously prevented the initiation of the flexural tension cracks. The typical failure mechanism that was observed during the tests is represented by crushing failure at the MgO board's compressive bending stresses side (top surface), with three specimens showing a de-bonding failure between the board and FRP component following the compression failure at excessive deflection.

The bending strength enhancement achieved by fibre reinforcing MgO boards can be well employed in the structural design to develop modular framing components including composite walling, roof and floor systems. In the following section an analytic formulation process is presented for modelling and predicting the flexural capacity of MgO-FRP composite section.

Figure 4: Load-deflection behaviour of composite FRP-MgO board (left) and crushing mode failure (right).

4 ANALYTICAL ESTIMATE FOR THE STRENGTH OF MGO-FRP COMPOSITE MODEL

In this section, flexure deformation principles are utilized to develop an analytical model to estimate the bending capacity of the investigated MgO-FRP composite section.

Oehlers and Bradford [13] demonstrated that plated reinforced concrete beams have similar characteristics to composite steel and concrete beams. Under bending load, the bonded plate gradually de-bonds from the reinforced beam and slip occurs between the plate and the beam so that there is partial-interaction. However, it is common practice to assume full-interaction when driving the stress resultants for design and, if necessary, allowance for the change in the behaviour can be adopted such as any small reduction in strength due to interface slip.

Idealized strain, stress and force diagrams for a MgO-FRP composite section are shown in Figure 5, where MgO board's maximum compressive strain (ϵ_{MgO}) is considered to be 0.0075 based on experimental testing on 20 mm side cubes. These curves, along with the assumption that the slip at the MgO-FRP interface may be ignored, form the bases for the flexural strength analysis of the MgO board.

The failure modes of the proposed composite MgO in flexure may be divide into two modes: (i) those where full composite action of MgO and FRP is maintained until the MgO reaches crushing in compression, and (b) those where composite action is lost prior to class (i) failure, e.g., due to the FRP peeling-off.

Figure 5: Full-interaction sectional analysis of side face for plated MgO board: (a) geometry, (b) strain distribution, (c) elastic stain distribution, (c') plastic strain distribution, (d) force distribution and (e) moment resistance.

In this study, the compressive stress block profile will be assumed in two formats: (i) an elastic stress profile, presented by a triangular stress distribution (Figure 5c) with a maximum MgO compressive capacity of $\sigma_{MgO} = 18.8$ MPa as estimated by experimental tests on 20 mm side cubes, and (ii) a fully plastic rectangular profile (Figure 5c').

The design bending moment capacity can be calculated based on calculating the natural axis depth, by Equation 1 (for the elastic stress model, Figure 5c) or Equation 1' (for the plastic stress model, Figure c'):

$$\frac{1}{2} \cdot \sigma_{MgO} \cdot w_{MgO} = A_{FRP} \cdot E_{FRP} \cdot \epsilon_{FRP} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{MgO} \cdot w_{MgO} = A_{FRP} \cdot E_{FRP} \cdot \epsilon_{FRP} \quad (1')$$

where w_{MgO} is MgO board design width, A_{FRP} is the cross sectional area of FRP strip, and from strain compatibility, the FRP stain (ϵ_{FRP}) can be defined as:

$$\epsilon_{FRP} = \frac{d_{FRP} \cdot \epsilon_{MgO}}{y_{NA}} \quad (2)$$

From Figure 5d, the bending moment capacity of the MgO-FRP composite section, $M_{MgO-FRP}$, can be determined by:

$$M_{MgO-FRP} = A_{FRP} \cdot E_{FRP} \cdot \epsilon_{FRP} \cdot Z \quad (3)$$

For Equations 1-3 to be valid, the straining of the FRP is limited to the ultimate strain, ϵ_{UFRP} :

$$\varepsilon_{FRP} \leq \varepsilon_{URRP} \quad (4)$$

Applying above calculation procedure (Equations 1 to 4) to determine the bending capacity ($M_{MgO-FRP}$) of the tested specimens for both considered stresses profiles (elastic and the plastic), the capacities were estimated to be 0.24 kN.m by the elastic model and 0.37 kN.m by the plastic model. When compared with the test results presented in Section 3.2 (Figure 6), it shows that both models are resulting in conservative estimates where the elastic model predicted the bending capacity at about 50% of the averaged test results for the maximum bending failure of the MgO composite section, while the plastic model was at about 80% of the test data. The reasonable agreement between the analytic plastic model and experimental results supports the adoption of the MgO crushing model as being the cause for the section failure, as observed during the experimental investigation.

Figure 6: Moment-deflection analytic model for FRP-MgO composite section in comparison with test results.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates the bending capacity of MgO boards in composite with FRP component as an attempt to consider the implementation of such composite members in framing modular units including composite walling, floor and roof systems. Given its high thermal resistance among numerous other benefits, MgO boards have a potential opportunity in being part of the structural framing system in the development of portable bushfire shelters. The experimental work presented in this paper showed that the bending capacity of unreinforced MgO boards can be enhanced by 167% when bonded with FRP component.

An analytical formulation for estimating the bending capacity of MgO-FRP composite section was developed based on assuming a plastic compressive stress profile to govern the failure mode and consequently the design approach. About 20% variation was found between the experimental and analytical model results which can be related to the accuracy of the experimentally determined compressive strain/stress values for both MgO board and the FRP component.

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